

Crystal-Phase Control of Ternary Metal Oxides by Solid-State Synthesis with Nanocrystals

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Figure S1. Histogram of the size distribution of the NC precursors used in this work.

Figure S2. XRD Rietveld refinements for the products obtained by annealing a) the (α - Fe_2O_3 +Cu) NC system and b) (γ - Fe_2O_3 +Cu) NC system.

Rietveld refinements were performed with Topas, refining for each phase the scale factor, size broadening (instrumental resolution determined empirically using SRM 1976c) and one thermal displacement parameter per atom type. Additional refinement parameters were the zero shift of the detector, the vertical displacement of the sample, and the coefficients of a Chebyshev polynomial describing the background. Figure S2 shows that for both systems CuO is present as second phase. Moreover, the estimated grain size for the annealed sample in a) is of 51 ± 2 nm for the CuFeO_2 phase and in b) of 14 ± 3 nm for the CuFe_2O_4 phase in agreement with the TEM analysis after annealing.

Figure S3. Planar SEM images together with the Cu, Fe and Cu +Fe EDXS maps for a) the film obtained after annealing α -Fe₂O₃ + Cu NCs and b) after annealing γ -Fe₂O₃ + Cu NCs both at 700°C for 30 min under N₂ atmosphere.

Figure S4. Identical location selected area electron diffraction images before and after annealing at 700°C for 30 min under N₂ together with the corresponding integrated patterns a) for (α -Fe₂O₃ + Cu) NCs and b) for (γ -Fe₂O₃ + Cu) NCs. The scale bar corresponds to 5 nm⁻¹.

Figure S5. Graphical representations of the crystal structures of a) $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ and b) CuFe_2O_4 (view along b axis), c) $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ and d) CuFeO_2 (view along a axis). $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ has a cubic crystal structure of an inverse spinel type characterized by Fe cations in two nonequivalent crystallographic sites, i.e., the tetrahedral F_A (purple) and octahedral F_B (green) sites.

Additionally, its structure features vacant cation sites F_B vacancy (indicated with dotted circles), which usually occur in octahedral positions, to compensate for the positive charge. These vacancies along with their similar crystalline structures favors the migration of copper ions and the transformation into the spinel CuFe_2O_4 .

Figure S6. a) XRD spectra of CuFeO_2 film obtained by sol-gel method (red line) and NC precursor reaction (black line); b) Electrochemical impedance spectra measured for the films in a) fabricated on FTO substrates. The obtained R_{cell} for each film is reported on the graphs.

The sol-gel method was reproduced from a previous work.¹ Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy was used to determine the electrochemical cell resistance (R_{cell}). CO_2 saturated 0.1M KHCO_3 was used as electrolyte. The spectra were measured at the open-circuit potential, using 41 points between 1 MHz and 100 Hz, a sinus amplitude of 20 mV and a pause time of 0.6 s between each frequency. The R_{cell} value was extracted from the Nyquist plot taking the value of $\text{Re}(Z)$ at the minimum value of $-\text{Im}(Z)$ before the charge-transfer arc. Being the cell, the electrolyte, the substrate equal for both samples, these results demonstrate that the films prepared from the nanocrystal precursors possess a lower electrical resistance than those prepared from molecular precursor via sol-gel chemistry, which is promising for future application as photoelectrodes.

Reference

1. Prövt, M. S.; Guijarro, N.; Sivula, K. Enhancing the Performance of a Robust Sol-Gel-Processed p-Type Delafossite CuFeO_2 Photocathode for Solar Water Reduction. *ChemSusChem* **2015**, *8*, 1359 – 1367.